

EFFECT OF PRE-TIGHTENING FORCE ON LAMB WAVE PROPAGATING BEHAVIOUR IN COMPOSITE BOLTED JOINTS

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we manufactured glass fibre reinforced epoxy composites by vacuum assisted resin injection processing. The composites were then used as the base material in the bolted joints, and the structural health monitoring process on the joints by Lamb wave was carried out. The relationship between Lamb wave signals and the pre-tightening force on the bolts was built. Results indicated that S0/A0 wave amplitudes decrease with the increasing of the applied load. Finite element simulation works were performed to capture the wave features. The application possibility of Lamb wave based structure health monitoring in the bolted joint-like composite structures was thus achieved.

1 INTRODUCTION

The need for stronger and lighter structures in aerospace field, ship engineering and automotive industries has driven the use of composite structures. Even though the structure length could be as long as a hundred meters, the maximum dimension of an integrative composite structure is limited into approximately 20 m in length by the manufacturing process such as the commonly used resin transfer moulding (RTM) [1, 2]. Therefore, bolted joints between composite components are necessary when manufacturing large size structures [3-5]. However, in real service conditions, damages, e.g. debonding and delamination, in the composite bolted joints are frequently initiated from the fastener holes, which further degenerated the structural reliability [6].

Structural health monitoring (SHM) system is defined to nondestructive and continuous monitoring structures using sensor arrays related to the fitness of an engineered component as it operates, so as to diagnose the onset of anomalous structural behavior [7, 8]. Guided wave could be generated by piezoelectric transducer on the studied structure. This transducer is very light, thin, and can be used as actuator and sensor, respectively [9]. Moreover, guided waves are sensitive to small-sized damages and could propagate over long distance [10]. Lamb wave is one of the guided wave modalities that generated by particle motions between the two free upper and lower surfaces in a thin plate-like medium [11]. By Lamb wave based SHM systems, there is no need to scan the entire object under consideration, and all of the data can be acquired from the single probe position.

The major emphasis of this paper is placed on the inspection of composite bolted joints based on Lamb wave propagation phenomenon. The bolted joints of interest were composed of two cases with different joint length-to-width ratios. The relationship between Lamb wave signals and pre-tightening force was discussed. Lamb wave propagation behaviour in the joints especially in the overlapped jointed region was carried out in the 3D finite element simulation.

2 EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS

2.1. MATERIALS AND MANUFACTURING PROCESS

We adopted vacuum assisted resin injection (VARI) process to manufacture the WGF/epoxy composites in the bolted joints, and Fig.1 showed the schematic diagram of the VARI. During the manufacturing process, we used a glass plate at the bottom of the VARI system as holder. After coating the release cloth on the holder, we placed four layers of woven glass fabric clothes. The stacking sequence of the plate was $[0^{\circ}/90^{\circ}]_4$. The final dimension of the manufactured WGF/epoxy composite laminates was $800 \times 800 \times 2$ mm³, and we cut it into the required dimension by a low speed diamond saw blade cutting machine under water protection. The through holes on WGF/epoxy

composite laminates were made by an electric drill, and the diameter of the holes was 10 mm. Two composite bolted joint cases were investigated: Case-A was the composite joints with single bolt, while the joints in Case-B had two steel bolts in them. As shown in Fig.1 and listed in Table 1, each case includes three categories of joints with the jointed length (L) to width (W) ratio (L/W) various from 1:1 to 3:1.

Table 1. Structural style and geometry dimension of the two studied composite bolted joints in the experiment.

Parameter	Case-A			Case-B		
W	40	40	40	60	60	60
L	40	80	120	60	90	120
L/W	1:1	2:1	3:1	1:1	3:2	2:1
L_{total}	450	410	380	450	410	380
Bolt location	$(L/2, W/2)$	$(L/2, W/2)$	$(L/2, W/2)$	$(L/2, W/4)$	$(L/2, W/4)$	$(L/2, W/4)$

Fig.1. Schematic diagram of the VARI manufacturing process and the two studied composite bolted joints.

2.2. LAMB WAVE INSPECTION SYSTEM

Fig. 2 shows the experimental setup for Lamb wave propagation in the composite bolted joints in Case-A and Case-B. The applied incident signal was 3.5 cycles of a 210 kHz sinusoidal tone burst enclosed in a Hanning window. The received signals were collected on an oscilloscope (MDO3021). The signals were then transferred to a PC for data processing through a GPIB interface. It should be noted that the transmitting transducers adopted in the experiments were piezoelectric (PZT) transducers, and they had a circular shape with the diameter of 10 mm and the thickness of 1 mm. All PZT transducers were bonded on the surface of the composite bolted joints using cyanoacrylate adhesive.

Fig.2. Experimental setup for Lamb wave inspection.

2.3 SIMULATION METHODS

FE simulations were conducted to interrogate the joint influence on Lamb wave propagation feature. In [12], we carried out the simulation work on woven composite laminates under low-velocity impact load. Also based on the developed three-dimensional FE method in the early work [13], we adopted 3D Hashin criteria and a user material subroutine to perform the Lamb wave inspection on the composite bolted joints. Simulation is carried out on Abaqus/Explicit platform, and the FE model with details is shown in Fig.3. Bolt location in the model is the same as the experiment in Fig.1 and Table 1. In the Lamb wave propagation simulation, the mesh size must be sufficiently small that should be at least 10 nodes per wavelength of the propagating wave [14]. The element type is 8-node C3D8R with a spatial resolution of 0.1 mm. This is more than ten times smaller than the smallest wave length of the Lamb waves in the considered frequency range. Two steps were performed in the simulation: pretightening force on the bolt was applied in the first step, and then the Lamb wave propagating behavior in the bolted joints was carried out in the second step.

Fig.3. FE model in the Lamb wave inspection simulation with details.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 LAMB WAVE IN COMPOSITES

Lamb wave has the nature of dispersion and multi-mode phenomenon, and it generally has symmetric (*S*) and antisymmetric (*A*) modes during the propagation [8]. In an isotropic medium, the constituent properties, geometry, wave direction, and frequency could affect the Lamb wave modes

[11]. Meanwhile, the wave modes maybe change when they meet the structural boundary and/or defects. However, due to the anisotropic properties, the wave propagation behavior in multi-layered composite laminates is very complex. The wave interactions depend upon not only the individual constituents but also their interface properties. In an N -layered composite laminate, there are totally six wave modes that could define a single guided wave mode in laminated composite plates [12]: two quasi-longitudinal (L), two quasi-shear vertical waves (SV), and two quasi-shear horizontal waves (SH). The Lamb wave can be generally described using its displacement field by satisfying Navier's displacement equations within each layer [28], as following:

$$\mu^n \nabla^2 \mu^n + (\lambda^n + \mu^n) \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mu^n) = \rho^n \frac{\partial^2 \mu^n}{\partial t^2} \quad (1)$$

where, ρ^i and λ^i , μ^i are density, Lamé constants for the i th layer, respectively. The selection of the appropriate Lamb wave mode and frequency could deeply affect the wave structure analysis processing due to the dispersive nature. This is further complicated during the propagation into anisotropic material due to the complex structural features. To find out the suitable frequency for effectively monitoring the composite bolted joint, we test the center frequency of the PZT wafer in Fig. 4. According to the test results in Fig. 3, the center frequency of the adopted PZT wafer is around 253 kHz. Therefore in the following damage localization study, we select 210 kHz as the excitation frequency.

Fig. 4. Center frequency of the adopted PZT wafer in the experiments.

3.2. PRE-TIGHTENING FORCE EFFECT

To investigate the pre-tightening force of the steel bolt on the guided wave propagation in the composite joints, we applied the torque from 20 to 30 N•m on the joints by a digital display torque wrench. The wave signals in the two cases with different torques were collected by the system in Fig. 2, and the signals were recorded with each increase of torque value. All the obtained data were compared and analyzed in terms of the wave amplitude. To evaluate the relationship between the waveform and the applied load on the composite bolted joints, we performed tensile tests of the joint

specimens. The tensile load-displacement curves of different bolted specimens were collected, and the corresponding wave structures of all the specimens during the tensile were captured. The load speed was also set as 2 mm/min at room temperature, and five groups of signals were collected at each load point. Fig.5 describes the relationship between the amplitude of *S0* and *A0* mode waves and the torque on the bolts in different composite joints cases. As shown in the figure, the amplitude of both the *S0* and *A0* mode waves shows an approximately decrease tendency with the increasing of torque. The wave amplitude in Case-A is generally larger than that in Case-B. As discussed, this is attributed to the wave reflection phenomenon in Case-B is severe than that in Case-A. To make the signal analysis processing easier, we applied the torque of 20 N·m on all the bolts since their *S0* and *A0* wave amplitudes are easier to distinguish among all the complex wave packages in the received signals.

Fig.5. Amplitude of *S0* and *A0* mode as the function of the applied torque on the bolt.

3.3 SIMULATION WORKS

It has been known that Lamb waves travel with the same velocity omnidirectionally and the wave front forms a circle in isotropic plates [15]. However, the wave velocity is subject to the direction of propagation in non-isotropic materials [16]. The wave structure of the composite bolted joints in the simulation and experiment is compared in Fig.6. It should be noted that the Lamb wave in the simulation is the U2 displacement. It is obvious that the *S0* mode is predicted successfully, and the simulation and experimental results match well. Like the received signal in experiments, two wave packages were found between *S0* and *A0* in the simulation. Minor differences between simulation and experimental results of the *A0* amplitude are attributed to the fact that the elastic vibration of *A0* wave at the composite plate edges in the experiment is difficult. Meanwhile, the distortion of the *A0* wave packets due to dispersion could also lead to the differences. As calculated by the relationship between propagation duration and the sensor-actuator distance in the FE, the predicted *S0/A0* wave velocity follows the dispersion features. Fig.6 shows the Lamb wave propagation feature when it propagates through the joint region. As can be seen, the fundamental *S0* and *A0* modes were captured well. It is worth mentioning that two significant phenomenon is found in Fig.6: Expansion of the excited Lamb

waves happened at the incident edge of the jointed plate, and when it is propagating from large cross-section to small area at the second edge, reflection and transmission occurs.

Fig.6. Displacement fields (U2) of Lamb waves in the composites bolted joints for an excitation frequency of 210 kHz obtained in the FE simulations.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This paper investigated the Lamb wave based structural health monitoring technology on two types of composite bolted joints with different L/W ratios. Amplitude of the Lamb wave varies with the applied torque on the joints. The S0/A0 wave amplitudes show a decrease tendency with the increasing of load. The built 3D FE model could capture the Lamb waves feature well when they are propagating in multi-layered composite laminates.

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